

Revolutionary Teamsters and Socialist Struggles Today: a forum

on

Bryan D. Palmer, *Revolutionary Teamsters: The Minneapolis Truckers' Strikes of 1934*. Leiden: Brill Academic Publishers, 2013 (Hardcover) and Historical Materialism Book Series. Chicago: Haymarket Books, 2014 (Paperback).

Workers of the World has invited three academics to review Bryan Palmer's recent book on the revolutionary teamsters of Minneapolis in the mid-1930s. Sean Purdy, S. Sándor John and Marcelo Badaró Mattos reviewed the book. Bryan Palmer commented.

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BRYAN PALMER

In many respects Bryan Palmer's masterful study of revolutionary Teamsters in the great Minneapolis strikes of 1934 is a continuation of his almost 40-year exploration of working-class studies in North America and Marxist historiography. The supremely rigorous research, poignant analyses and theoretical sophistication of the research into one of the most important strikes of the 1930s in North America recalls his first forays into Canadian labor history in the late 1970s and early 1980s.¹ Like the work of the E.P. Thompson he has so thoroughly studied,² this is a historian's history: exhaustive archival research in diverse locales in the United States, thorough analysis of secondary sources on the strikes and the 1930s labour and socialist movement and a vibrant narrative of events, people and places that delves into the political and social history of the period.³ While not directly engaging with wider historiographical debates on Marxism and history, the Teamsters study is unapologetically materialist and informed by Palmer's long engagement with Marxist theory.⁴ Perhaps most importantly, this study of Trotskyists in the trucking sector in Minneapolis is eminently political and explicitly intended to provide lessons for today's working-class struggles, a concern long expressed in Palmer's prolific historical and political writings.⁵

Revolutionary Teamsters originated as a chapter in Palmer's second volume of his biography of American Trotskyist James P. Cannon. It includes three introductory

¹ PALMER, Bryan D. *A Culture in Conflict: Skilled Workers and Industrial Capitalism in Hamilton, Ontario, 1860-1914*. Montreal: McGill-Queen's University Press, 1979; PALMER, Bryan D. and KEALEY, Gregory. *Dreaming of What Might Be: The Knights of Labor in Ontario, 1880-1900*. New York: Cambridge University Press, 1982.

² PALMER, Bryan D. *The Making of E.P. Thompson: Marxism, Humanism and History*. Toronto: New Hogtown Press, 1981; PALMER, Bryan D. *E.P. Thompson: Objections and Oppositions*. New York and London: Verso, 1994.

³ For other examples of Palmer's richly-detailed histories, see *Cultures of Darkness: Night Travels in the History of Transgression*. New York: Monthly Review Press, 2000 which is based on an undergraduate class that he taught in the 1990s; *James P. Cannon and the Origins of the American Revolutionary Left, 1890-1928*. Urbana, IL: University of Illinois Press, 2007; *Canada's 1960s: The Ironies of Identity in a Rebellious Era*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 2009. Palmer has also published dozens of detailed empirical and historiographical articles in history journals since the 1970s and edited many collections of essays. Later this year, Brill Academic Publishers will publish a two-volume collection of Palmer's empirical and theoretical articles. It is also worth noting that Palmer has also been long involved with the prominent bilingual Canadian labour history journal, *Labour/Le Travail*, serving as Review Editor from 1983 to 1997 and as Editor from 1997 to 2015. A highly committed supervisor, Palmer has also supervised dozens of graduate theses in labor and social history since the 1980s at Simon Fraser University, Queen's University and finally Trent University where he has been a Canada Research Chair in Canadian Studies since 2001.

⁴ PALMER, Bryan D. *Descent into Discourse: The Reification of Language and the Writing of Social History*. Philadelphia: Temple University Press, 1990.

⁵ For some examples of Palmer's explicitly political writings, see PALMER, Bryan D. *Solidarity: The Rise and Fall of an Opposition in British Columbia*. Vancouver: New Star Books, 1987; PALMER, Bryan D. *Capitalism Comes to the Backcountry: the Goodyear Invasion of Napanee*. Toronto: Between the Lines Press, 1994.

chapters on the historiography of the strikes, the 1930s U.S. labor movement, the concept of the mass strike and the political economy of Minneapolis; 18 short, lucid chapters chronicling the ups and downs of the struggle, the key players and events and analyzing the progress of the strikes; a conclusion on the lessons to be learned today; and a useful appendix on Trotskyism in the United States in the 1930s. The 300-page book is richly illustrated with a total of 28 striking images including photographs, paintings, leaflets, newspapers and paintings.

Downplayed by many historians who focus solely on the Communist Party (CP) or bureaucratic trade unionism, Palmer emphasizes the centrality of the Minneapolis strikes (as well as similar socialist-led strikes in San Francisco and Toledo) as critical moments in the class struggle of the 1930s which played a crucial role in the revival of the workers' movement after several years of depression-era misery, demoralization and defeat. What was new in the 1934 strikes was the existence of a solid cadre of revolutionary workers in the trucking sector in Minneapolis belonging to the Communist League of America (CLA), the first U.S. Trotskyist organization formed in 1928 by sympathizers of the international dissident component of the international communist movement led by Leon Trotsky. Expelled from the established and much-larger CP, a small group of CLA militants worked tirelessly in the first bleak years of the Depression to provide a pole of ideological opposition to both the Stalinists in the CP and the conservative labor bureaucrats of the American Federation of Labor (AFL) to organize workers (drivers and coal-heavers) in the largely non-union trucking sector in the city. Led by the Dunne brothers – Ray, Miles and Grant – Carl Skoglund and the non-Trotskyist ally Bill Brown, workers in the trucking sector organized a resilient rank and file union and through a series of strikes that faced brutal state repression consolidated their unions and effectively ended the open-shop regime in the city. It was one of the first salvos in the great working-class upheaval of the 1930s that witnessed the formation of the Congress of Industrial Organizations (CIO) and important advances in wages, working conditions and union protections for millions of American workers.

What is also new in Palmer's analysis is his focus on the key role of CLA in the leadership of the strike. Along with the established militants and new recruits on the ground, the CLA sent its leading organizers such as James Cannon, Max Shachtman and Albert Goldman to Minneapolis to aid in strike organization and mobilization. Stressing the necessity of a democratic and rank-and-file based strike, they organized regular mass meetings, a daily strike paper and a Women's Auxiliary. All in all, he highlights the cohesive nucleus of Trotskyist leadership that remained free from the conservatism of the Democratic Party and the reformists of the Farmer-Labor government, developed a winning strategy and mobilized workers to confront the hostile and repressive forces of capital and the state. Palmer is not uncritical of the CLA and the strikes' leadership, highlighting their sometimes sketchy assessment of the reformist state government during the strike and relations with other trade unions in the years after the strikes that have been overlooked in the wake of the decisive victory in 1934.

If Palmer deftly outlines the “skeleton” of the 1934 strikes - organization, ideology, negotiation and conflict – he also provides the human “flesh” of the movement with a narrative punctuated by many mini-biographies, colorful story-telling and sensitive analysis. The three Dunne brothers who were central Trotskyist militants in the strike are portrayed in detail and labelled “Propagandistic Old Moles” for their persistent propaganda and incipient agitation in the first years of the Depression and contrasted with their older brother Bill who remained with the CP even writing a scurrilously sectarian pamphlet against his younger brothers’ Trotskyist activities. The contradictory gender relations involving the important Women’s Auxiliary in the strike is handled with the necessary nuance as is the reformism of the moderate Farmer-Labour state government in Minnesota. Palmer’s use of various primary sources such as the strike newspaper, leaflets, posters, personal and internal party correspondence and the memoirs of militants provide fascinating detail on the day-to-day progress of the strikes. Palmer’s exploration of the often conflictual personal and political styles of the Trotskyists’ strike committee and various other key players deftly rounds out his overall analysis.

Palmer is concerned throughout the book with drawing the lessons of the 1934 strikes and the importance of revolutionary socialist ideas and leadership in today’s struggles. As he states in the introduction: “Minneapolis in 1934 matters because, in 2013, it has things to tell us, ways of showing that the tides of history, even in times that seem to flow against change, can be put on a different course.” (p.7) This is an utterly principled intention that cuts against much recent historical scholarship that feigns objectivity or disinterest in the fight for a better world in the present. It is an optimistic assessment for socialist and social movement militants today that recalls Gramsci’s famous dictum on the necessity of “pessimism of the intellect, optimism of the will”. In the present context of global economic crisis, war, environmental devastation and oppression, highlighting historical examples where committed minorities of socialists helped to mobilize and lead masses of workers to decisive victories is an essential intellectual and political task.

If the determination, shrewd strategy and innovative tactics of the 1934 Minneapolis strikers and the Trotskyist militants give us an inspiring historical inspiration, it is clear that the strategies, tactics and forms of today’s struggles would be decidedly different. Class composition and relations have shifted, employers and the state command massive resources of repression, technology and communications aid and complicate today’s struggles, multiple oppressions cut against class solidarity, most trade unions have ossified bureaucratic structures and practices, established left parties have adopted neoliberal politics and the revolutionary left fights against the current to establish embryonic footholds in the diverse struggles that we confront on a daily basis. Surely the keys to success today in any struggle would require an intelligent remapping and rethinking of the political lay of the land and innovative strategies and tactics appropriate to twenty-first capitalism. Yet thanks to Bryan Palmer’s inspiring history of Teamsters and Trotskyists in the 1930s we have a great place to begin this renewed project of socialist struggle.

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To start with conclusions: Bryan D. Palmer's *Revolutionary Teamsters* is a book for today. This account of class battles in Minneapolis during 1934 is must reading for those intent, in 2015, on changing the world we live in. Vivid, in fact thrilling, is its account of how workers ground down by economic depression and union-busting rose up in victorious struggle. Gainsaying those from both right and "left" all too smugly certain that it couldn't be done, they paved the way for mass union organizing drives that followed on a national scale.

Minneapolis was but one of an infinity of places where it needed to be done, and far from the only opportunity for successful class struggle at the time.⁶ What made the difference, as Palmer convincingly shows, was the determined nucleus of revolutionary Marxists – Trotskyists – at the heart of his story. Up-front about his sympathies, Palmer is equally so when it comes to his intentions. To those who would cast yesteryear's revolutionary Teamsters as voices from a long-dead past, Palmer provides explicit rejoinders, emphasizing that despite significant contrasts, there are important social and political parallels between what working people faced then and the situation today.

I would argue that the key conclusion to be drawn from his account is this:

Revolutionary Teamsters shows what even a small revolutionary nucleus can do, even in a difficult situation, if it is serious – in deeds as well as words – about bringing revolutionary politics into the class struggle. As Palmer writes, "the coming together of teamsters and Trotskyists in Minneapolis in 1934 provides a concrete case of just what can be accomplished by workers guided by those who have a revolutionary perspective" (p. 4), even if the immediate objective is as basic as establishing real union representation.⁷ That is a living lesson for today.

Some may concede that hard class struggle informed by revolutionary politics was necessary in 1934, even that it might be desirable in 2015. Few seem to believe that it is *possible*, let alone act accordingly, today. *Revolutionary Teamsters* brings welcome lessons, and inspiration, for those willing to show not only that it should, but that it must and can be done in the here and now. He describes the labor officialdom of 1934 as "far more reticent than it was radical" (p. 275). You can say that again when it comes to their descendants of 2015. How to meet today's burning need to organize the unorganized, with or without immigration papers, and carry out the urgent revitalization of the labor movement? Today's version of the hidebound labor bureaucrats who stood in the way of

⁶ From this standpoint, *pace* Palmer, "uneven and combined development" provides little guidance to understanding class-struggle victories there.

⁷ On p. 220, Palmer quotes Cannon's statement that in the combination of revolutionary leadership and workers' organized militancy, "one can see the power that will conquer the world."

victory in 1934 can't and won't. Only the kind of revolutionary outlook and program advanced by those who led the struggle to victory in Depression-ravaged Minneapolis can make this possible.

It is commonplace for activists to bemoan the sorry state of labor today, with a "leadership" good only for bringing one defeat after another. What brought it about? Perhaps the biggest factor of all was the purge of reds who built mass unions in the first place. *Revolutionary Teamsters* is a contribution to reviving the historical memory of what they did and how they did it. Yet Palmer's book is not an uncritical account of this heroic chapter in labor and revolutionary history. Nor is it a hagiography of Trotskyist leader James P. Cannon or his comrades among the strike leaders of 1934. Critical analysis is front and center.

So too – and this is one of the pleasures of the book – is the human story. Who made up this handful of hard-bitten reds that, facing daunting odds and obstacles, dug deep into the Minneapolis coal yards? Why were men and women newly awakened by class struggle "oddly jubilant" (p. 83) on the eve of big battles? When the cops busted heads and shot unarmed workers in the back, how did the militants of Teamsters Local 574 organize care for the victims and regroup to win? How did they manage to put out a daily strike paper, *The Organizer*, that thousands of workers made the vibrant voice of their own aspirations? Above all, how *did* this small group of revolutionaries successfully organize workers battered by economic crisis, facing relentless employer hostility, after seemingly endless retreats "led" by worse-than-useless labor bureaucrats beholden to the parties and politicians of the capitalist status quo?

Because of, not despite, their politics. The allegedly esoteric doctrine espoused by Cannon's then-isolated cohort was no esoteric footnote, as mainstream historians would have it, in this rollicking story of rough and ready Teamster rebels. Nor was it a sidelight to the "nitty-gritty" of organizing. Instead, as Palmer makes clear, it made the story possible: it *was* the nitty-gritty of how they built a powerful union – which wound up rocking the Northwest and beyond – from hard-pressed truck drivers together with the coal-shovelers, crate-heavers, "chicken-pluckers," and others despised and excluded by the hidebound craft-unionists who lorded it over the International Brotherhood of Teamsters.

"Going with the flow" is no way to win. As part of the Trotskyist nucleus then called the Communist League of America – itself scorned and derided by currents that fancied themselves the big-league players of leftist politics – they had assimilated the lesson that preparing real victories means swimming against the stream. This too is vitally relevant today, when what Cannon, Trotsky and their comrades called opportunism is deeply ingrained amongst all too many on the labor left. (To cite one example, organizing rallies for low-wage workers are repeatedly turned into photo ops for Democratic politicians. For another, see most left reactions to the recent Greek elections.)

"Jugar con reglas del patrón, es segura perdición." Roughly translated, this means "if you play by the bosses' rules, you lose," a slogan eagerly picked up from revolutionaries

by immigrant workers at New York's Hot and Crusty restaurant who waged a difficult, successful union organizing drive – and won a union hiring hall – in 2012.⁸ In an oft-quoted retrospective of the Minneapolis strikes, Cannon insisted: “Our people didn’t believe in anybody or anything but the policy of the class struggle and the ability of the workers to prevail by their mass strength and solidarity.”⁹ This is crucially pertinent to events in the U.S. today, as the labor officialdom preaches submission to the bosses’ anti-labor laws, endlessly subjugating the labor movement to the same Democratic Party that leads the charge against education workers, wages endless wars abroad, and ramps up police-state measures “at home.” To unchain workers’ power today, it really is essential to build an opposition guided by the lessons of class struggle; that is, by revolutionary politics.

Palmer’s book sheds light as well on the very current topic of police violence against the oppressed. Mass protests from Ferguson, Missouri to New York City have brought claims from “official” (Democrat-aligned) leaders that it’s a question of a “few bad apples,” and that racist police violence can be reformed away. More radical forces insist the problem is systemic; young Marxists have sought to popularize the chant that “Only revolution can bring justice.”

The Trotskyist-led Teamster insurgents of 1934 stressed that repression is the *function* of the “special bodies of armed men” at the core of the capitalist state. When police bullets wounded at least 67 unarmed strikers on “Bloody Friday” (20 July 1934), *The Organizer* drove home the lesson that police are “the Uniformed Protectors of Profits.” Guiding the strikes to victory in the face of this organized state violence required an understanding of this basic class insight plus a sophisticated sense of strategy and tactics informed by the lessons of previous class struggles, not only in the United States but internationally. Union militancy was necessary but not sufficient; again, *revolutionary* leadership was required.

Capitalist or working-class politics? As co-thinkers of Leon Trotsky, Minneapolis Teamster leaders knew that for unionists to defeat powerful employers backed by capitalism’s politicians and state power, they had to go beyond trade-unionism “pure and simple” and enter the terrain of politics.

Revolutionary Teamsters is an antidote to the conventional wisdom snake-oil tale that Roosevelt’s National Labor Relations Act, Labor Board and federal mediators embodied victories for the working class. As savvy veterans of battles going back to Wobbly days, Minneapolis Trotskyists showed their ability to outmaneuver local politicians, and sent some of those mediators scurrying out of town with their tails between their legs. The felt need to maneuver in the face of “Farmer-Labor” governor Floyd Olson’s support in the labor movement is understandable – but the book details important weaknesses in their approach regarding this capitalist politician. Trotsky was, moreover (as Palmer notes), quite critical of what he saw as his U.S. comrades’ tendency towards conciliation of

⁸ See “Hot and Crusty Workers Win With Groundbreaking Contract,” *The Internationalist* (November 2012), <http://www.internationalist.org/hotandcrustyworkerswin1211.html>.

⁹ James P. Cannon, “The Great Minneapolis Strikes,” *Fourth International*, May 1944.

“Rooseveltian” trade-unionists. From the standpoint of the exiled Red Army organizer, principled intransigence in the fight for the political independence of the working class forms the basis for smart tactics in difficult situations.

If that was a lesson of Bolshevism, so too was Lenin’s insistence that labor’s power must be brought into the fight against all forms of oppression if labor, and all those downtrodden by capitalist society, are to win. Key to the Minneapolis struggle was the fighting alliance Local 574 forged with the unemployed and with farmers facing ruin in the capitalist crisis. Palmer highlights the importance of the union’s Women’s Auxiliary, refuting historians who have put it down as an expression of submission rather than what it was: one of the most vital weapons in for defeating local rulers ruthlessly determined to keep the women and men of 574 in their “place.”

So no, the past is no “foreign country” for those intent on learning how to organize a different future. Today, some of the less deluded mouthpieces of capitalism admit to a sneaking suspicion that the working class will not forever take a beating without striking back. Glimpses and flashes have emerged, in immigrant workers’ revival of International Workers’ Day; in the May Day 2008 longshore union action against the Iraq and Afghanistan wars that shut down all 29 ports on the West Coast; in work stoppages there and in Brazil for the freedom of radical black journalist Mumia Abu-Jamal; in the increasingly open discontent of low-wage workers throughout the U.S., the determination of strikers standing up to the robber oil barons and a number of organizing campaigns. Of course we cannot pinpoint when broader struggles will erupt. What we can clearly affirm is that for a successful counteroffensive to be waged, organizing now on the basis of a program to win the class struggle is of the greatest importance.

Through the many and varied sources Palmer brings to bear, we hear the voices of those who built on that basis in the years leading up to the victories of ’34. Among them are legendary militants such as the Dunne brothers and “illegal” immigrant revolutionary Carl “Skogie” Skoglund; less-known but pivotal activists like Jack Maloney, Carlos Hudson and the Dakota Sioux Trotskyist Ray Rainbolt, commander of the Union Defense Guard;¹⁰ picket-line defenders and Women’s Auxiliary organizers like Clara Dunne, Marvel Scholl and the indomitable “Mrs. Carle”; together with Cannon and other Trotskyist leaders who helped beat a path to victory in Minneapolis. Readers looking towards revolutionary future for the world workers movement will get the satisfying sensation of being in conversation with some of “our people” from the past, who have much to pass down to us today.

¹⁰ Rainbolt was one of several Sioux and Ojibwe (Chippewa) revolutionary Teamsters who issued a humorous rejoinder to claims that the union was “un-American” (p. 264n).

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In this second decade of the twenty-first century, any analysis of current social conflicts would recognize that we are witnessing social struggles of great proportions in diverse places around the planet. Mass protests have multiplied with some reaching the proportions of true political revolutions (even if many times they are incomplete) and almost all have questioned the current bases of capitalist accumulation (if not capitalism itself). Surely they were impelled in great part (but not exclusively) by the crisis detonated in 2008 and the “austerity” packages used by governments to combat it: from the “Arab Spring” (2010-2011) to the protests against the deaths of the Mexican students (2014) passing through the diverse “Occupy” movements in North America (and other places), by the Spanish 15M or the “June Days” of 2013 in Brazil, among many others. Analyses of these movements have highlighted among their principal characteristics, the profile of the protestors – more heterogeneous, young and educated -, the “horizontal” organizational forms and the rejection of traditional leaderships and organizational instruments typical of the struggles of the working class since the nineteenth century such as parties and unions.

There are good reasons for such a rejection including: the exclusionary character that dominates the workers’ movement with representation almost always restricted to the formal sector of the working class in which precariousness, informality and elevated unemployment rates are widely evident (in the North as much as the South of the planet despite different dimensions); the bureaucratic practices of union leaders more interested in maintaining their relative privileges than effectively representing class interests; and the clear commitment to the ruling order by the leaderships of the immense majority of parties born through workers’ movements that still possess parliamentary/electoral weight. Yet the recent movements also face flagrant difficulties in relation to their capacity to guarantee that their explicit or implicit demands in mass mobilizations result in positive outcomes on the political level or even to take advantage of the moments of greater mobilization to create more permanent spaces of organization and struggle. Is this situation inevitable? Would it not be possible to (re)connect the recent mass mobilizations and their participants to the more traditional organizations of the working class, potentializing the former and revitalizing the latter? Can the history of the struggles of the working class in the twentieth century, without pretension to give scholastic “lessons” to current generations, raise discussions about past experiences and processes that could be useful in the search for solutions to the impasses of the present?

It is exactly in this sense that Bryan Palmer’s book, *Revolutionary Teamsters*, may be read as very rich contribution to analyses of the workers’ movement in North America in the context of the capitalist crisis that emerged in 1929, but also as a stimulus to debate alternatives in the present situation of social struggles. After all, the subject of the book

– the truckers’ strikes in Minneapolis in 1934 – brings together a group of events that were central turning points in relation to questions of mobilization and organization in the decade. A context of capitalist crisis prevailed with the whole range of consequences for the working class that we all know so well today: a brutal rise in unemployment, the reduction of real wages of those who have work, the absolute and relative pauperization of the majority of the population as well as the anti-union politics of the bosses (combined with the passivity/complicity of the union bureaucracies encrusted in the craft unions dominant in the American Federation of Labor/AFL) and the combination of strongly repressive measures and mechanisms of social assistance (and at the most anti-cyclical interventions) of the state.

In 1934, after various years of the evident decline of the capacity of intervention of the workers’ movement, a few mass strikes initiated a significant shift in the situation of American unionism. This was the case of the San Francisco general strike led by the stevedores of the city’s port that paralyzed around 125,000 workers at its peak. Similarly, the Toledo strikes, initiated in auto-parts factories, had a great impact that counted on the strong support of the unemployed sector of the working class. Treated in the second chapter of Palmer’s book, these strikes were characterized by the strong union and political presence of the left who organized the strike movements and together with the Minneapolis strikes of the same year provided a decisive impulse to the reorganization of American unionism that in the following years would result in the rise of the Congress of Industrial Organizations (CIO).

The truckers’ strikes in Minneapolis and the movements with which they connected – in a city with a little more than 450,000 inhabitants (the fifteenth largest city in the United States at the time) there were 30,000 unemployed and around 120,000 depending on some form of public assistance in the first years of the 1930s – are highlighted as one of the great events of the time and have been evaluated by other studies, all of which are addressed by Palmer in the first chapter of the book. Even so, *Revolutionary Teamsters* is distinguished by a strong dose of originality for diverse reasons. First, by the emphasis he gives to the importance of a left-wing leadership distinct from the vanguard organized in Toledo by the American Workers’ Party (an organization with a proletarian base and a fluid reformist program spurred on by the radical events of 1934) and the leaders of the San Francisco strikes linked to the Stalinist Communist party in its most sectarian phase at the beginning of the 1930s. Minneapolis witnessed the surprising encounter between a small (really small with only a half dozen militants at the beginning of the process), but decided groups of militants from the communist left opposition – Trotskyists organized in the Communist League of America – and the largely unorganized workers in the trucking sector.

Palmer’s analysis demonstrates that such leadership had a decisive role in the grass roots organization of the trucking sector, widening the professional category and the mobilized base beyond the drivers and their helpers to involve all workers involved in the loading and unloading of goods. Studying this grass-roots organization in the 1930s, especially in Chapter 4 – accomplished through the patience of the revolutionary “old mole” referred

to by Marx – Palmer reminds us that it was not done in detriment to the occupation and renovation of the existing space of the established union (Local 574 of the General Drivers' Union of the AFL). Establishing anterior relations with the sector most disposed to mobilize for union recognition, the left vanguard was able in 1934 to transform the union into a more combative organization with a wider industrial logic of representation. The result was evident with the increase in the number of workers organized in the sector from between 75 and 175 in 1933 (p.37) to some thousands (2-3 thousand in April and close to 7 thousand in the middle of the year) who fought for union recognition during the strikes of 1934 (p.60).

The emphasis on the importance of the organizational work of the Trotskyist leadership leads the author to highlight the role of James P. Cannon, one of the principal leaders of the Left Opposition in the period and the subject of an important biography already published by Palmer.¹¹ Cannon did not accompany the actions in Minneapolis from a distance but involved himself directly on the ground, especially from the final days of the second strike in May 1934 when he brought to the city his experience of decades as an organizer of movements to strengthen the Strike Committee constructed to sustain the struggle (see chapter 10). Cannon also represented a point of convergence between the local mobilizations in Minneapolis and the wider conjuncture of the class struggle on the national level. As a way to understand the role of Trotskyists in the wider movement, Palmer includes an appendix to the book with a synthetic recuperation of the trajectory of Trotskyist militants and their organizations in the United States in the years before the 1934 strikes.

All the emphasis the analysis places on the role of leadership should not lead us to a rash judgment that it was the only element responsible for the dimensions of the movements in Minneapolis in 1934. On the contrary, Palmer's chief interest is in registering the specific form of the virtuous "dialectic of leaders and led" that occurred in this process. Such a dialectic is visible to the reader because the author presents a detailed narrative – supported by memoirs, testimonies, official documents and, especially, extensive research in periodicals of the period – of the events of the strikes in February, May and July/August. The narrative is certainly designed to highlight important particularities of the movement such as the degree of the extremely detailed preparation of all the activities undertaken by the militants, their preoccupation with mobilizing the unemployed (Chapter 6), the involvement of families (with emphasis on the role of women, dealt with in Chapter 7) and the disposition to confront harsh repression. The latter may be observed as much in the conflicts between strikers/picketers and the police and hired militias, such as in the "Battle of Deputies Run" that occurred in the May strike (see Chapter 9) as in the clashes of July/August when the National Guard was called up and martial law decreed against the strikers by the supposedly "progressive" governor of the Farmer-Labour Party. This latter battle was an even more violent confrontation, especially

¹¹PALMER, Bryan. *James P. Cannon and the origins of the American Revolutionary Left, 1890-1928*. Chicago, University of Illinois Press, 2007.

“Bloody Friday” on July 20 when dozens of strikers were arrested, many were wounded by bullets and one man was killed as a result of his wounds (see Chapters 14 and 15).

The descriptive richness of the narrative of these events is strongly integrated with a theoretical-analytical approach that is the principal source of the originality of Palmer in relation to those who preceded him. In a creative form, he employs the theory of uneven and combined development to explain the process. In Chapter 3, Palmer recuperates the history of the workers’ movement in Minneapolis, demonstrating that significant advances in struggles at the end of the 1910s were followed by a series of defeats for workers in the 1920s and the rise of a reactionary and anti-union sector, organized around the Citizens’ Alliance, that pushed left-wing unionism to the margins and even relegated the class collaborationist mediation of conflicts by the AFL, highly relevant in other areas of the country, to a secondary role. However, in the midst of the powder keg of contradictions generated by the economic crisis after 1929, the relative “backwardness” of the local workers’ movement became the principal reason for the privileged position of the city as a platform for the workers’ movement to “leapfrog” towards the most important manifestation of class struggle at that time in the United States. In Palmer’s words: “labor’s very failures meant that there were spaces for radicalism to breath, for it could not be suffocated by mainstream counterparts almost entirely lacking in strength” (pp. 33-34). This same explanatory approach allows the author to explain how the ruling class exacted revenge in the first years of the 1940s against the leaders and conquests of the strikes such as the small economic victories of the February strike, the recognition of the union after the May strike and to a certain point the surprising victory of the July/August strike that resulted in wage increases, improvements in working conditions and a significant impulse for union reorganization not only locally, but in many other cities (see Chapter 21).

Yet the importance of Palmer’s book goes well beyond the history of the strikes themselves that he tells. The central point is that Minneapolis in 1934 “matters because [today] it has things to tell us” (p.7). Which things? Among the “lessons” of this process, Palmer stresses: “a sense of both the necessity *and* possibility of rebuilding the kind of revolutionary organization that can simultaneously nurture a creative leadership *and* encourage and develop the militant combativity of the working class. Struggles that secure gains in new causes have to be fought through, planned, and mobilized in order to be won”. Without doubt, this book rescues this “important chapter in the history of the possibility of class struggle” (p.268).

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My thanks to *Workers of the World* for providing a forum for the discussion of my *Revolutionary Teamsters: The Minneapolis Truckers' Strikes of 1934*. The commentaries by Sean Purdy, Marcelo Badaró Mattos, and S. Sándor John are laudatory and generous. It is gratifying to read reviews that value history, not as some kind of precious artifact, but as a living process, with relevance in the here and now. I wrote the book to make the elementary point, too often lost in the swirl of playful postmodernisms or detailed accounts of cultural minutiae, that history matters. To be sure, as Sean Purdy points out, we cannot recreate the past in current political struggles, and just how much has changed and what that means for how we approach the project of socio-economic transformation in our times are critically important questions, with which we must engage rigorously. That said, it is important not to lose sight of continuities, of principles that do not die. Too much is perhaps often made of how *everything* today is so relentlessly different than *anything* we may have known in the past. This kind of positioning has a way of obfuscating the obvious, obliterating the outlines of the knowable in a charade of endless consideration, however sophisticated, that manages to immobilize active resistance rather than guide it in fruitful ways.

What is most striking in the response to *Revolutionary Teamsters* is that, as what Sándor John calls “a book for today,” it elicits reactions that come out of today as well. Purdy, John, and Badaró Mattos rightly read my account of arguably one of the most important strikes of the 20th century with an eye to what can be learned about how we might struggle today. They express differences of nuance and subtlety, but they all agree that the crucial importance of a revolutionary Trotskyist left in Minneapolis in 1934 mattered decisively. This registers with them in terms of appreciating the importance of the lack of such a presence, for the most part, in the class struggles of the current period.

How different this is from what we might label the standard academic review, an early example of which is Richard Oestreicher’s short assessment in the British journal, *Social History*. Oestreicher praises *Revolutionary Teamsters*’ “energetic narrative,” delivered with what he describes as “skill and verve,” building on “laborious delving in primary sources.” He acknowledges that the leadership of the strike was well-served by its revolutionary commitments, in as much as this dedication to a cause steeled the determination of the Minneapolis trade union leadership. But for Oestreicher the victory in Minneapolis somehow happened “in spite of their Trotskyist politics, not because of them.” Managing to virtually ignore the book’s narrative, Oestreicher bypasses how the Minneapolis revolutionaries functioned as architects of a momentous labour mobilization in a non-revolutionary situation. As an academic reviewer Oestreicher finds it perplexing how anyone could actually believe in the possibility of revolutionary politics, and his review ends with a dismissal of all such fine sentiments, calling for an “effective analysis

of contemporary world politics” and an “appropriate strategy for the Left in the current moment.” What that might be, however, and how it might draw on the history of the teamsters’ strikes of 1934 is never addressed. Ironically enough, the academic historian, seemingly guided by the need for an objective account, is able to ignore what happened in the past if it does not suit his sensibilities about what should be happening today.¹²

Left critics of *Revolutionary Teamsters*,¹³ such as Teamsters for a Democratic Union founding figure, member of Solidarity, and *New Politics* co-editor Dan La Botz can fall into the same trap. La Botz, in what is arguably the most critical assessment of my treatment of the 1934 teamsters’ strikes, takes umbrage at *any* criticisms of the strike leadership, both during the confrontation in 1934 and for years afterwards. He blurs nuances, misrepresents positions, and argumentatively asserts that there are problems where others find strengths. Thus, Sándor John describes the reconstruction of class struggle in *Revolutionary Teamsters* as “vivid, in fact thrilling,” and another Solidarity reviewer, Barry Eidlin calls the book “the most vivid, in-depth, meticulously documented account” of the 1934 events, “written with a novelist’s attention to narrative tension and plot development.” La Botz, in contrast, bemoans an “all-too-dense narrative,” likening *Revolutionary Teamsters* to “a political tract from another era.” Whereas Badaró Mattos rightly sees my book’s attention to the dialectic of leaders and led as unfolding in the “descriptive richness of the narrative of events,” highlighting how the Left Opposition of the Communist League of America was able to advance the cause of trade unionism in Minneapolis, La Botz complains, yet again, of the “limited degree” to which “the Trotskyist leadership’s functioning in Local 574” is revealed.¹⁴ Sean Purdy sees the

¹² Richard Oestreicher, “Review of *Revolutionary Teamsters*,” *Social History*, 40 (February 2015), 123-125.

¹³ In what follows I will often allude to three reviews that have been collected digitally: Dan La Botz, “Trotskyist Teamsters of the 1930s – An Attempt to Draw the Lessons,” first published in *New Politics*; Barry Eidlin, “Minneapolis 1934 Strike Revisited,” first published in *Against the Current*; and Alan Wald, “‘A Seemingly Incongruous Alliance’: Trotskyists and Teamsters in 1934,” first published in *Labour/Le Travail*, all in “The Year 1934: Three Reviews of Bryan Palmer’s *Revolutionary Teamsters*,” <http://www.solidarity-us.org/site/node/4213>, accessed 20 March 2015.

¹⁴ La Botz wonders whether the Trotskyist leadership made decisions first in their cell, fraction, or branch, or if those decisions were arrived at through dialogue with workers’ leaders and activists. I can only question whether La Botz has read the book. There is abundant discussion of how the Trotskyist leadership, which rallied to it virtually all of the militant class fighters within the ranks, had existed within the trucking sector for some time. It clearly connected with workers, listened to them, and incorporated their tactical and strategic suggestions. Then, through their Communist League of America (CLA) discussions, these Trotskyists arrived at strategic orientations. Once they were in positions of strike leadership, these CLAs conveyed to the Teamster membership suggestions about strike developments and how to advance the struggle in open, democratic union meetings, where union decisions were taken. From the establishment of the Trotskyist-led volunteer organizing committee that orchestrated the first February 1934 strike through to the development of the Strike Committee of 100, the relations of Trotskyist leaders and the rank-and-file led are part of the “dense narrative” that La Botz finds unsatisfying. Had he been more open to reading it carefully, he would have answers to some of the questions he poses. The issue of party fractions and their role in situations like Minneapolis has been elaborated on in E. Tanner, “Revolutionary Teamsters: The Minneapolis Truckers’ Strikes of 1934 – A Review and Commentary,” Parts I & II, *Workers Vanguard*, 1052/1053 (19 September/3 October 2015), <http://www.icl-fi.org/English/wv/1052/palmer.html>, accessed 20 March 2015. Tanner claims that *Revolutionary Teamsters* fails to address the work of the “Teamster fraction of the Minneapolis CLA branch.” This is overstated and it misunderstands precisely how Minneapolis in 1934 differed from Trotskyist trade union work in the 1933 New York hotel strike or among the Progressive Miners of America in Illinois. In both cases the struggle to build and sustain disciplined

human “flesh” that *Revolutionary Teamsters* puts on the skeleton of working-class leadership as illuminating; he enjoys the “mini-biographies, colorful story-telling and sensitive analysis” that is used to portray figures at the center of the strike, like the three Dunne brothers. La Botz, in contrast, following a position first articulated by Alan Wald, dismisses “one-dimensional ... portraits of Teamster leaders that border on caricature.” This is not so much a matter of there being ‘no accounting for tastes’, as it is a clear indication of how much preference is determined by politics.

La Botz (and Wald as well) wants more on women and the support Auxiliary that they organized, while other reviewers (such as Eidlin) comment on the book’s attempt to “highlight and assess the central role that women played in the strike.” What is at stake in this discussion, however, is highlighted in Sándor John’s decisive judgment that *Revolutionary Teamsters* refutes “historians who have put [the Women’s Auxiliary] down as an expression of submission rather than what it was: one of the most vital weapons for defeating the political rulers ruthlessly determined to keep the women and men of 574 in their ‘place’.” Radical feminists such as Elizabeth Faue have represented the Women’s Auxiliary as part of the gendered construction of working-class Minneapolis,¹⁵ and while I do not deny the importance of this in the making of class relations in the 1930s, I stake out an entirely different appreciation of what was involved in how women mobilized to support the teamsters’ strikes. Wald, in particular, argues that talking to surviving relatives of those involved in the 1934 conflicts will give us a fuller picture.

fractions of CLA cadre was essential but also flawed and incomplete, revealing both strengths and weaknesses within the Left Opposition’s trade union work. In both cases, albeit to differing degrees, the CLA fractions were struggling to achieve influence within established unions, integrate headstrong fraction members incompletely assimilated to the program of revolutionary trade union work, and overcome marginalization by entrenched, conservative labour leaderships. The CLA presence as a fraction thus had to be, as Trotsky advised his American Left Opposition comrades in 1933, disciplined but far from open in its operations. Among the Minneapolis teamsters, however, the CLA fraction *was* the CLA itself, largely because of the size of the local and the importance of the work among the teamsters to the branch. To talk of the fraction as somehow different than the CLA branch or, indeed, the local CLA strengthened by those Left Opposition leaders brought in from New York City like Max Shachtman and James Cannon, is to miss the main point. After breaking through various barriers with its orchestration of the February strike, this CLA leadership was the *de facto* leadership of the truckers’ insurgency, effectively displacing the International Brotherhood of Teamsters-American Federation of Labor-affiliated officialdom. In this situation the fraction could function openly and effectively as the ‘party’, and it did so adroitly, not with the purpose of establishing a revolutionary Soviet Minneapolis (which it was alleged was happening by a viciously red-baiting mainstream press), but with the intention of building militant class struggle unionism. Trotsky, recognizing that such situations would be rare for the revolutionary Left Opposition, nonetheless anticipated the possibility of these kinds of circumstances, and wrote: “The more the influence of the Communist fraction grows in the union, the more boldly and openly will it fling out the banner of its party.” See Leon Trotsky, “Trade Union Problems in America,” 23 September 1933, in *dog Days: James P. Cannon vs. Max Shachtman in the Communist League of America, 1931-1933* (New York: Prometheus Research Library, 2002), 591-593. For a discussion of how the International Communist League/Spartacist League critique of *Revolutionary Teamsters* around the issue of fractions and class struggle caucuses relates to perspectives of contemporary trade union work see “Spartacists Repudiate Class-Struggle Caucuses: Belated rationalization for abandonment of trade-union work,” http://www.bolshevik.org/statements/ibt_20141231_spartacists_caucuses.html, accessed 20 March 2015.

¹⁵ See Elizabeth Faue, *Community of Suffering & Struggle: Women, Men, and the Labor Movement in Minneapolis, 1915-1945* (Chapel Hill and London: University of North Carolina Press, 1991).

Could more be done in the way of oral histories of the strike and its participants?¹⁶ Absolutely. Might the search for other sources reveal a cache of fresh documentation? Certainly that is possible. For women, ethnic groups, and the particular case of native Americans, of whom I have identified six strike supporters, and about whom La Botz insists more should be told, useful information may well surface that will expand our understandings of the 1934 events in Minneapolis greatly. No such evidence came to my attention and none is cited by La Botz. Still, discoveries happen; those seeking may well find. There remains much to be done, for instance, even on the ground of politics, with a fuller exploration of the importance of the Farmer-Labor Party, which governed the state of Minnesota, of undoubted importance.¹⁷ A good history of the reactionary Citizens Alliance exists, but there remains much to explore in terms of the local civic officialdom and its administration of the city amidst an intense period of class struggle.¹⁸ The context of Minneapolis's "privilege of backwardness," which I adopt from Trotsky's discussion of uneven and combined development, is unconvincing to Sándor John but suggestive to Badaró Mattos, and I am more than willing to concede that the full story of Minneapolis's political economy and how this material context relates to the workers' mobilization of the Great Depression needs fuller elaboration.¹⁹ *Revolutionary Teamsters* claims no definitiveness. This said, however much more we may come to know about the 1934 strikes and the circumstances in which they developed, their meaning and significance in the history of American class struggle is unlikely to be so altered that we can ever discount the importance of the Trotskyist leadership that guided Minneapolis's teamsters to victory.

History matters. Not because it is interesting, and lively, and full of human richness, diversity, and complexity, although all of this is true enough, and quite important. History matters because, while it can neither predict the future nor assure us of the outcomes we want, it is all that we as historical materialists have to go on in our attempt to see the present as the raw material of social transformation. La Botz wants to restrict our vision to victories for industrial unionism, suggesting that my claims about revolutionary Trotskyism miscue. But as much as 1934 *was* about consolidating a union, as long as that consolidation was the victory of revolutionaries, there existed the ever-present twinned danger of compromising the independence of the Trotskyist left or of having it

¹⁶ There already are many oral history sources relating to the 1934 strikes, including the material presented in Philip A. Korth, *The Minneapolis Teamsters Strike of 1934* (East Lansing: Michigan State University Press, 1995).

¹⁷ Unpublished MA and PhD theses are suggestive, although their interpretations demand challenging interrogation. See, for instance, George Dimitri Tselos, "The Minneapolis Labor Movement in the 1930s," PhD dissertation, University of Minnesota, 1971; Kristoffer O. Smemo, "The Politics of Labor Militancy in Minneapolis, 1934-1938," MA thesis, University of Massachusetts-Amherst, 2011; and for the later 1930s, Smemo, "A 'New Dealized' Grand Old Party: Labor and the Emergence of Liberal Republicanism," *Labor: Studies in Working-Class History of the Americas*, 11 (Summer 2014), 35-60.

¹⁸ William Millikan, *A Union Against Unions: The Minneapolis Citizens Alliance and its Fight Against Organized Labor* (St. Paul, MN: Minnesota Historical Society, 2001).

¹⁹ The issue is not so much that Minneapolis was a locale of combined and uneven development *per se* (in the orthodox Marxist sense of the term), but that the presence of Trotskyists *along with the relative backwardness of the labor movement*, allowed a vanguard element, for a time, to leapfrog over backwardness, advancing the class struggle and necessitating a marshalling of antagonists against its leadership.

succumb to repression. Almost all of La Botz's critical commentary on my moderate criticisms of the Minneapolis leaders relates to post-1934 developments, where I suggest that the leadership of the 1934 strikes followed a post-1936 course in their relations with trade union officialdoms in other cities and states that deprived them of a base of support in the ranks that could only result in their being targeted in future times of conflict and retrenchment. The issue is not, as La Botz would have it, whether the Trotskyists could realistically have undertaken the arduous task of building party fractions throughout the Midwest and developing left-wing caucuses inside the International Brotherhood of Teamsters locals. I am well aware of how difficult this would have been, perhaps even impossible. But in the absence of this kind of active development of a revolutionary presence in the wider union and, tellingly, in the apparent failure of the Minneapolis Trotskyist teamster leadership to use its important regional voice, *The Northwest Organizer*, to differentiate itself from "the pro-Rooseveltian trade unionists" lay the seeds of an accommodation that would bear the bitter fruit of repression. Trotsky warned of this, writing of the "terrible danger" that confronted the Minneapolis victory and those who made it. In June of 1940 Trotsky discussed all of this with Farrell Dobbs, James Cannon, and other leading Socialist Workers Party (SWP) figures. He was adamant that, for all its strong points, *The Northwest Organizer* was "a photograph of our adaptation to the Rooseveltians." He noted that the Dobbs-edited paper, proposed "a trade union policy, not a Bolshevik policy. ... You are afraid to become compromised in the eyes of the Rooseveltian unionists. ... If you are afraid, you lose your independence and become half Rooseveltian. In peacetime this is not catastrophic. In wartime ... they can smash us."²⁰

Roughly two weeks later, on 29 June 1940, Roosevelt signed what would become known as the Smith Act into law, criminalizing those who so much as advocated overthrowing the government. A year later, 27 June 1941, the Minneapolis SWP offices were raided; 23 Trotskyists and Minneapolis teamster leaders were eventually brought to trial on a variety of charges, with 18 convicted of Smith Act-inspired counts in December 1941. What Trotsky had predicated had come to pass. To address this and to relate it to the policies of the Minneapolis Trotskyist leadership in the aftermath of 1934's advances, is not, as La Botz and Eidlin suggest, allowing "sectarian tendencies to show through." It is grappling with the actual history of the revolutionary left, addressing its victories and defeats with suggestions of what could have been done differently. Not to do this is to abdicate our responsibilities as both historians of labour and the left, and leftists attentive to history.

This history matters because the 1934 Minneapolis strikes, led by Trotskyist revolutionaries, remind us that revolutionaries can indeed win, even in the most inauspicious of circumstances. But in order to win, revolutionaries must be true to their principles, living by them through the thick and thin of protracted class struggle. Those principles are not a loose and elastic container into which anything can be poured, just as

²⁰ Leon Trotsky, "Discussions with Trotsky, June 12-15 1940," *Writings of Leon Trotsky [1939-40]* (New York: Pathfinder, 1969), 271-273.

they are not dogmatically rigid and incapable of adapting to complex realities. Against my insistence that the victories achieved in 1934 in Minneapolis were more thoroughgoing than those achieved elsewhere – and can one really argue with this when the San Francisco waterfront strike or the Toledo auto parts battle and their outcomes are scrutinized? – La Botz claims that it was not the historic Left Opposition that won so much for workers, but “far left leadership of any sort.” This echoes, in some ways, the view that the Trotskyist leadership led so effectively in Minneapolis in 1934 not so much because of its politics but in spite of them.

This, in my view, is not the lesson that should be drawn from an examination of the class struggles of 1934. Rather, the significance of the class struggle leadership of the revolutionary Trotskyists who set the pace for events in Minneapolis in 1934 tells us that just the opposite was true 80 years ago. There are those who are in denial about this history. They take the positions that they do because history matters to the politics they would like to see operative right now. For some, anything to the left of Barack Obama will do. Others, if they look at struggles like those that unfolded in Minneapolis and elsewhere in 1934, will insist on thinking otherwise.